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The first species of *Pseudomedon* from the Himalaya, with additional records of *P. kazakhstanicus* (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae: Paederinae: Medonina)

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A b s t r a c t : *Pseudomedon bengalensis* nov.sp. (India: West Bengal: Darjeeling), the first representative of the genus from the Himalaya and the second species from the East Palaearctic east of Middle Asia, is described, illustrated, and distinguished from its congeners. A supplement to a recently published key to species is provided. The genus now comprises twelve species in the Palaearctic region. Additional records of *Pseudomedon kazakhstanicus* ASSING 2008 from Kazakhstan are reported.

K e y w o r d s : Coleoptera, Staphylinidae, Paederinae, *Pseudomedon*, Palaearctic region, Himalaya, India, taxonomy, new species, key to species, additional records.

Introduction

Pseudomedon MULSANT & REY 1878 of the subtribe Medonina previously comprised 20 species, nine unrevised species of doubtful generic affiliations from the Afrotropical and the Australian regions and eleven revised species from the Palaearctic region (ASSING 2008, 2009, 2011). One of the Western Palaearctic species is adventive also in South America (ASSING 2009). For a key to the Palaearctic species, a supplement to this key, and a catalogue see ASSING (2009, 2011).

Material from the collections of the natural history museum in Genève examined in the course of a revision of Himalayan *Lathrobium* GRAVENHORST 1802 included two specimens of a species previously attributed to *Lathrobium*. An examination revealed that they, in fact, represented an undescribed species of the medonine genus *Pseudomedon*. Also, since the latest contribution to the Palaearctic representatives of *Pseudomedon*, additional material of the recently described *P. kazakhstanicus* ASSING 2011 has become available.

Material and methods

The material referred to in this study is deposited in the following public institutions and private collection:

MHNG Muséum d'Histoire naturelle Genève (G. Cuccodoro)

MNHUB..... Museum für Naturkunde der Humboldt-Universität Berlin (J. Frisch, J. Willers)

cAss..... author's private collection

The morphological studies were conducted using a Stemi SV 11 microscope (Zeiss Germany) and a Jenalab compound microscope (Carl Zeiss Jena). For the photographs a digital camera (Nikon Coolpix 995) was used.

Head length was measured from the anterior margin of the frons to the posterior margin of the head, elytral length at the suture from the apex of the scutellum to the posterior margin of the elytra, and the length of the aedeagus from the apex of the ventral process to the base of the aedeagal capsule.

Results

Pseudomedon kazakhstanicus ASSING 2008

Material examined: Kazakhstan: 7 exs., Ile river, Aidarly, 12.IV.1984, leg. Kastcheev (MNHUB); 3 exs., same data, but 6.X.1984 (MNHUB); 3 exs., same data, but 16.IV.1983 (cAss); 8 exs., Ile river, Karagach, 2.IX.1986, leg. Kastcheev (MNHUB, cAss); 2 exs., Syrdaria river, Shaulder, 28.V.1985, leg. Kastcheev (MNHUB).

Comment: *Pseudomedon kazakhstanicus* is currently known only from Kazakhstan (ASSING 2008, 2009).

Pseudomedon bengalensis nov.sp. (Figs 1-4)

Type material: Holotype ♂: "India W. Bengal, Darjeeling distr., Ghoom-Lopchu, 2000 m, Besuchet-Löbl, 14.X.78 / Lathrobium sp.?, det. G. de Rougemont 1999 / Holotypus ♂ *Pseudomedon bengalensis* sp.n. det. V. Assing 2011" (MHNG). Paratypes ♂: same data as holotype (cAss).

Description: Body length 3.2-3.4 mm. Coloration: body yellowish-red, with the anterior two thirds of abdominal segment VII infusate; legs and antennae dark-yellowish.

Head (Fig. 1) approximately as long as broad; lateral margins behind eyes subparallel or weakly converging posteriad; posterior angles moderately marked; punctation, except for some punctures on frons, extremely fine and dense, barely noticeable; interstices with very shallow microsculpture. Eyes large, 0.7-0.8 times as long as postocular region in dorsal view. Antenna moderately slender; antennomere III approximately as long as II, approximately 2.5 times as long as broad; IV-VIII of gradually decreasing length and decreasingly oblong; IX approximately as long as broad; X indistinctly transverse.

Pronotum (Fig. 1) weakly oblong, approximately 1.05 times as long as broad and 1.05

times as broad as head; punctuation extremely fine and dense; interstices without distinct microsculpture and glossy.

Elytra approximately 1.1 times as long as, and much broader than pronotum (Fig. 1); punctuation extremely dense and fine, but more distinct than that of head and pronotum.

Abdomen slightly narrower than elytra; punctuation very fine and dense; interstices with shallow microreticulation; posterior margin of tergite VII with palisade fringe.

♂: sternite VII not distinctly modified; sternite VIII distinctly oblong, its posterior margin truncate, not concave or distinctly excised (Fig. 2); aedeagus approximately 0.35 mm long, shaped as in Figs 3-4.

E t y m o l o g y : The specific epithet (adjective) is derived from West Bengal, the province where the type locality is situated.

Figs 1-4: *Pseudomedon bengalensis* nov.sp.: (1) forebody; (2) male sternite VIII; (3) aedeagus in lateral view; (4) ventral process of aedeagus in ventral view. Scale bars: 1: 1.0 mm; 2: 0.2 mm; 3-4: 0.1 mm.

Comparative notes: In order to account for the new species, the key in ASSING (2009) is modified as follows:

- 1 Pale-coloured species, forebody or whole body yellowish, reddish, or yellowish-brown. 1a
- Dark-coloured species, at least head and abdomen dark brown to blackish.....8
- 1a Anterior two thirds of abdominal segment VII distinctly infuscate and contrasting with remainder of body. ♂: sternite VIII and aedeagus as in Figs 2-4. N-India: West Bengal.....
.....*P. bengalensis* nov.sp.
- Abdominal segment VII not distinctly contrasting with remainder of body. ♂: sexual characters different. Absent from the Himalaya.....2

Distribution and natural history: The type locality is situated near Ghoom, Darjeeling district, West Bengal province, North India. The specimens were collected at an altitude of 2000 m.

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Zusammenfassung

Pseudomedon bengalensis nov.sp. (Indien: West-Bengalen: Darjeeling), die erste Art der Gattung aus dem Himalaya und die zweite Art aus der Ostpaläarktis östlich von Mittelasien, wird beschrieben, abgebildet und von anderen Arten der Gattung unterschieden. Eine kürzlich publizierte Bestimmungstabelle wird ergänzt. Die Gattung ist derzeit mit zwölf Arten in der Paläarktis vertreten. Weitere Nachweise von *Pseudomedon kazakhstanicus* ASSING 2008 werden aus Kasachstan gemeldet.

References

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